

FACTORS MOTIVATING IP STUDENTS' EDUCATION DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM

¹ CHRISTIAN A. CAPUNONG, ²JOHNNY S. BANTULO, EdD,
³KRIS ANJIELA M. MAÑAUL, MA

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, Graduate School

General Santos City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7081709>

Published Date: 15-September-2022

Abstract: The investigation aimed to determine and analyze the common factors motivating the IP learners' education during the Covid-19 pandemic as a basis for a proposed intervention program in the IP schools at Maasim 2 District, Division of Sarangani. The researcher made use of the descriptive cross-sectional survey design. Additionally, the study utilized Walberg's Educational Productivity Theory, Ryan and Deci Self-Determination Theory, and Weiner Attribution Theory. Moreover, the study found that among the 107 respondents of the study, the five schools had a high level of motivation. It found out that the common factors motivating the IP learners' education were teachers' involvement, the learning environment, the family/parent involvement, peer involvement and their personal interest. Hence, the study came up with an intervention program to address the common factors motivating the IP learners. It would initiate programs and activities that would help increase the level of personal interest, peer involvement and parent/family involvement in motivating IP students.

Keywords: Education, motivating factors, IP learners, Covid-19 pandemic, intervention program plan, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The access to education and services had narrowed down in most countries worldwide and it bent disturbances that affected millions of learners. Currently, according to studies, the pandemic has been the cause that adversely impacted the educational systems of the world. Day by day, it made peoples' life unsafe that many institutions had to shut down their operations, limited their workers workload, and disturbed the delivery of quality education for all people (Cohen, Baber, et al., 2020; Onyema, Eucheria, et al., 2020).

In the Department of Education (DepEd) of the Republic of the Philippines, the tireless agency asserted to endure and innovate the learning modality of the curriculum. Many accepted the innovative method of learning that DepEd developed, and among them were from the far-flung area of the country where mostly Indigenous People (IP) live (Sidel, and Faustino, 2019; Estremera, 2021).

However, as observed in last school year's data when there was no pandemic yet, IP learners had struggles performing academically. Now that the delivery of the learning is unfamiliar, many learners learning opportunities such as lively interaction, immediate feedback, and social-emotional development could not be instantly addressed. Besides, implementing

those alternative delivery modalities can be unlikely and risky for teachers and learners in the IP communities. Exposing oneself outdoors can cause respiratory illness carried by the new corona virus. But, somehow, the IP learners still persisted to study. Words of admiration showed up for the learners for their perseverance, diligence and effort even when a catastrophe occurred (Burgess and Sievertsen, 2020; Vaishya, Javaid, Khan, and Haleem, 2020).

Along with the aforementioned situations and circumstances, there must be reason/s that inclined IP learners to continue and keep the course of their education amidst the Covid-19 pandemic. To date, several studies have investigated the same research work. As the analysis mentioned, there were factors considered to stimulate learners' decisions, actions, and conduct. But none among the studies addressed the factors motivating IP learners in a geographically isolated and disadvantage area during pandemic (Srinivas and Venkatkrishnan 2016; Xie and Ritchie, 2019).

Accordingly, the researcher needed to determine the factors motivating IP learners' education in the public schools of Maasim 2 District, Division of Sarangani during the covid-19 pandemic. And the researcher hoped to provide insights that would help create an intervention program for the learners in the IP communities.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

This study determined and analyzed the factors motivating IP learners' education during the Covid-19 pandemic as Basis for an intervention program in school at Maasim 2 District, Division of Sarangani.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the factors motivating IP learners' education during the Covid-19 pandemic?
2. What intervention program could be formulated based on the findings of the study?

1.2. Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the following theories: Walberg's (1980) Educational Productivity Theory, Ryan and Deci's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, Weiner's (1974) Attribution Theory.

The research was grounded by Walberg's (1980) Educational Productivity Theory. The theory stated that the learning influences affected learner's educational performance. Based on the investigation of academic achievement, Walberg used methods to identify the factors that affect a learner's educational performance. The Educational Productivity Theory was among the few empirically tested approaches in school learning and was based on the analysis and integration of more than 3,000 studies. The study emphasized that learners' atmosphere and immediate environment affect learners' knowledge.

This study was also based on the Self-Determination Theory of Human Motivation as cited by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan (1985). In this context, it indicates to what moves us to act. The study looked at the natural factors towards growth and outlined two types of motivation (intrinsic and external motivation). This theory has identified ways to motivate learners to learn at all levels of education. Stimulation leads people to act purely to satisfy their curiosity or desire for mastery. All other actions are prompted by motivation, driven by social values. Motivations are promoted by moods of competence, autonomy, and relatedness. These methods will help develop interventions that will encourage learners and provide learners with satisfaction.

Finally, this research study was anchored on Attribution Theory cited by Weiner (1974). The theory explained that learners engage in the learning environment because of a desire to develop behavioral causes. The Theory of Attribution assumed that people try to determine why people do what they do, that is, traits that cause behavior. The context of this theory emphasized individuals' interpretation of events and how it relates to their thinking and behavior. After an event, learners create unconscious causal explanations (attributions) for the consequences. As stated, attributions vary in locus, stability, and controllability. Locus mentions whether the cause is internal or external to the separate. Resilience refers to whether the reason is fixed or likely to change. Controllability refers to whether the source is within or outdoor the individual's control. These influence emotions, which in turn drive motivation in upcoming tasks and engage in learning because of a personal need to develop new qualities.

1.3. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study is shown in Figure 1. It consists of a variable, the factors motivating IP learners' education, and how this would become the basis for an intervention program.

As pointed out, proper identification and evaluation of student motivation are highly related to effectiveness in learning activities. These factors effectively develop learning because motivation plays an essential role in performance (Makransky, et. al., 2019; Yeager, and Dweck, 2020).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The research utilized a cross-sectional research design, where it collected data from a group of respondents at a single point in time. Besides, the cross-sectional survey would be used if the primary purpose was to determine the prevailing state of phenomena. Survey research design is striking flexible and can appear in various forms (Creswell, and Creswell, 2017; Nardi, 2018). The research method was utilized in the study to determine the factors motivating IP learners' education.

The cross-sectional survey in the study provided information on the frequency of the factors that influences IP learners' education during the pandemic period. We gathered relevant data using a validated researcher-made questionnaire. The data were collected from the enrolled grade 6 IP pupils in the public schools of Maasim 2 District, Division of Sarangani. The data gathered had been analyzed to determine the factors motivating IP learners' education during the covid-19 pandemic.

2.2 Research Locale

The study was conducted at Maasim, a coastal municipality in the province of Sarangani. The municipality has a land area of 500.43 square kilometers or 193.22 square miles, constituting 13.9% of Sarangani's total area, and comprises 64,940 or 11.61% of Sarangani's total population.

The locale of the study were Cabansal M. Larry Elementary School, Kyumad Integrated School, Lebe Integrated School, Langaran Elementary School and Datal Basak IP Integrated School. These schools were the public schools recognized as the IP schools in Maasim 2 District, Division of Sarangani, Region XII. Mainly, their pupils/learners belonged to the different tribes of Indigenous People of the Philippines, such as T'boli and B'laan.

2.3 Research Respondents

The study was participated by the grade six (6) pupils that were enrolled in the following IP schools in Maasim 2 District: Cabansal M. Larry Elementary School, Kyumad Integrated School, Lebe Integrated School, Langaran Elementary School, and Datal Basak IP Integrated School, the school year 2020 - 2021. Based on the school registry of enrolled Grade six (6)

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 5, pp: (17-26), Month: September - October 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

learners in the recognized IP schools in Maasim 2 District, Division of Sarangani. The researcher had acquired the total population of every school to form a test group.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

Schools	Number of Respondents
School A	14
School B	33
School C	29
School D	23
School E	8
TOTAL	107

2.4 Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a self-made instrument. The instrument formulation was based on the transcribed initial interview from IP learners and gathered related items from the various references online and related literature. It was a survey questionnaire that would help determine the factors motivating IP learners' education during the covid-19 pandemic. The researcher gathered related items that were subject to face validation and content from various works of literature. The validated result retained 25 items for the survey questionnaire and comprised five parts: Part 1- Survey Questionnaire for Personal Interest, Part- Survey Questionnaire for Peer Involvement, Part 3- Survey Questionnaire for Family/Parental Involvement, Part 4- Survey Questionnaire for Teacher Involvement and Part 5- Survey Questionnaire for Learning Environment.

After which the original items were determined, the first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections included and integrated. The final copies were presented to the panel of experts for approval. The last revision was done incorporating the corrections. The experts' comments and suggestions were taken and followed before it was made ready for distribution and administration.

Scale	Description	Interpretation
4	Strongly Agree	It means that the level of motivation is very high.
3	Agree	It means that the level of motivation is high.
2	Disagree	It means that the level of motivation is low.
1	Strongly Disagree	It means that the level of motivation is very low.

The Likert Scale was used to describe the factors Motivating IP learners. According to Batterton and Hale 2017), the method involves people to tick a box / blank in response to multiple items about an attitude, item, or incentive. It is common to treat the quantity achieved from a rating scale immediately as measurements by calculating averages or, more generally, any arithmetic operations.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher-made survey questionnaire had been subjected to validation. The first draft of the self-made questionnaire was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations. Then a letter was given to the expert validators to evaluate and validate the researcher-made questionnaire based on the following criteria:

Clarity of directions and items. The vocabulary level, language structure, and conceptual level of respondents. The test direction and items are written clearly and understandably. First, presentation/ organization of items. The items are presented and organized logically. Second, suitability of items. The manner of items appropriately represented the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes to be measured.

Third, adequateness of items per category. The items equally represented the coverage of the research. The number of questions per area is enough as needed in the study. Fourth, attainment of the purpose. The instrument as a whole achieves the objectives on which it was constructed. Each question requires a specific answer to measure only behavior, and no aspect of the questionnaire suggests bias of the researcher. Fifth, scale and evaluation rating system. Scale adapted is appropriate for items.

After the validation of experts, the final number of items had been determined and included in the questionnaire. Test items that had been verified to be valid and essential for the survey remained, and then final copies were reproduced. The researcher sought the expert consent and approval.

Upon the panelist's approval, the researcher gathered the necessary data and information needed for the study. The conduct of the study was following the safety protocols imposed by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) on the emerging COVID-19 disease, wearing of the Personal Protective Equipment, Disinfection and Maintaining at least 3feet/1meter Social Distance. Afterward, a letter of permission was given to the Schools Division Superintendent, the Public Schools District Supervisor, the School Heads, and the teacher-advisers of the said locale of the study. After that, the researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire to ensure that directions and instructions were provided. The researcher gave the respondents the option to write their names, and then they were given time to answer the questions.

2.6 Statistical Tools

The study used the mean and ranking to analyze the data gathered. The formula for weighted mean is $X = \frac{\sum X}{N}$, X is the mean, $\sum X$ is the sum of the scores, and N is the number of items in the instrument. It was used to treat subproblems 1, describing the factors motivating IP learners.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Factors Motivating IP Learners' Education During Covid-19 Pandemic

Table 2 shows the factors motivating IP learners during the covid-19 pandemic. The data collected determined personal interests, peers, family/parents, teachers, and the learning environment were the factors involved in the motivation of IP learners.

Personal Interest. The table shows IP learners were evaluated, and it was found out that the level of motivation regarding their interest was high, acquiring a mean of 2.63. The result came from the mean score of 2.7 from school E, school C with 2.63, school A with 2.61, and school D with 2.6, while school B got 2.59.

The results implied that IP learners agreed that this factor drove them. Learning in this time of pandemic was their preference, to experience the new modality of the school year that could facilitate their learning at home.

The literature confirmed the factors that determined the high level of persuasion and interest in reaching its goal. The element has indications of learners' interest and persistence in schooling. moreover, they performed and tried to do something because they believed it would help and benefit them, especially in their education (Stewart, Lim, and Kim 2016; Martin and Elliot, 2016). It was emphasized that the education of learners is affected by their motive, and it shows its vital role towards their academic or educational performance (Haider, et. al., 2015; Urquijo and Natalio, 2017).

Peer Involvement. The data revealed that the level of motivation of IP learners about their peer involvement was high, acquiring a mean of 2.74. It came from school E with the mean score of 2.8, followed by school D with 2.77, school B with 2.74, school A with 2.73, and lastly, school C with 2.65. The findings showed that IP learners agreed that peer was among the factors motivating their education. Their peers made their co-peer felt a sense of belongingness, support, and assisted each other in response to the new learning modality (Hosen, et. al., 2021; Zhao, Cao, Li, and Li, 2022). It indicated that peer-influenced the education of learners. Peer factors could back up the wholesome start of the educational activities. In support of its peers, teaching in both public and private, as investigated, support and help individuals that struggle with mental breakdown and suffer emotional pressure. Peer simplified and changed the conduct of individuals who cannot function due to depression and anxiety (Demirtaş-Zorbaz and Ergene, 2019; Fortuna, et. al., 2019).

Family/Parental Involvement. It showed on the data that all five schools got high remark. The level of motivation of IP learners regarding the involvement of the family/parents was high. The acquired mean was from school A with the mean score of 3.00, school D with 2.982, followed by school C with the mean score of 2.978, school B with the mean of 2.96, and school C with 2.95. The results showed that IP learners agreed that family/parent involvement was among the factors that motivated their education. IP learners showed that their family/parent's economic status excessively induced them. Aside from that, their family/parents' encouragement and involvement in their education are among the indicators that keep the course of their learning the family has difficulty supporting their needs (Bodovski, et. al., 2022; Calandri, et. al., 2022). Among research assessed parental or family involvement was among the factors that induced learners to continue performing in education. It confirmed that family participation had been optimistically impacted learners' performance in schools. The investigation stated that the involvement of a student's family directly affected the learning behavior. It benefited them with emotional stability, improved social skills, and increased academic success (Masnan, et. al., 2017; Muller, 2018).

Teacher Involvement. It is presented in the table that IP learners had acquired a very high level of motivation from teachers with a mean of 3.4. The findings got mean scores from school E with 3.55 mean, school C with 3.45, school B with 3.35, school D with 3.33, and school A with 3.328 mean score. The results revealed that teachers' involvement was among the factors that had highly driven the motivation of IP learners. They agreed that they were occasionally supported and encouraged to continue education during this pandemic. Teachers made IP learners understand the importance of education, and teachers conveyed their concern to their learners despite the challenges experienced.

The investigation revealed teachers' involvement significantly affected learners' educational performance. As reviewed, including personal attention, dealing with learners' problems, the treatment, showing respect for each other, and communication skills confirmed to be the indicators of learners' motivation from teachers (Poulou, 2017; Ida, 2017). It emphasized that teachers' appearance was relatively significant to learners' educational conduct. Their virtuous character and actions made learners realized and stimulated them to perform (Bal-Taştan, et. al., 2018; Baier, et. al., 2019). Learning Environment. Last, the data from the table showed that the level of learning environment motivating IP learners is high, with a mean of 2.85. School B acquired the highest mean score among the schools, with 2.91. School C with the mean score of 2.9, school D with 2.84, school E with 2.83 mean scores, and school A with the mean score of 2.78. The result revealed that IP learners agreed that the learning environment, the setting of the learning modality this pandemic school year, was also among the stimulants that kept IP learners' education on course. The place of learning made them agree to support their learning there because it was safe from the fatal disease called Covid-19. Hence, it would provide a lot of time for the learners because knowledge will be at home.

It implied that the learning environment was another factor involving motivation. The learning environment would enhance the well-being and learning of learners, and it made learners felt safe and secure, met their basic needs such as food, and creates an environment to be comfortable (Karusala, et. al., 2017; Ekeh and Venketsamy, 2021). Similarly, the physical environment develops and improves through activities and materials in diverse performance areas. The learners are more eager to study when they perceive the learning environment as constructive and encouraging (Edwin-Ezeoka, and Obidike, 2020; Seden, Wangmo, and Dorji, 2020; Choi and Cho, 2020).

Comparably, among research also stated that self-motivation plays an important role in the success of learners in the institutions. In the study, it was found out that intrinsic factors were considerably higher than extrinsic factors. These motivating factors prior to the conclusion were positively associated with statistical impact in the academic performance. Learners who possessed engaging qualities such as self-exploration, compassion, and career focus, and community force had a positive impact on their academic performance. Aside from that, based on the assessed data in relation to the academic performance following motivation; self-motivation, and personal interest, greatly correlated with the learners' educational success (Bailey, and Phillips, 2016; Özen, 2017; Theobald, 2021).

The Level of Factors Motivating IP Learners

Indicators	Mean Score of Every Respondent School										
	A	Description	B	Description	C	Description	D	Description	E	Description	MEAN
Personal Interest											
I want to experience the new learning modality.	2.57	High	2.33	Low	2.21	Low	2.57	High	2.38	Low	2.41 (Low)
I think learning using self-learning modules will facilitate my learnings this pandemic time.	3.00	High	2.70	High	2.83	High	2.87	High	3.13	High	2.91 (High)
I feel I will enjoy the new learning modality I am taking.	2.29	Low	2.27	Low	2.31	Low	2.35	Low	2.13	Low	2.27 (Low)
I will have the chance to study more often at home.	3.07	High	3.21	High	3.45	High	3.04	High	3.50	High	3.25 (High)
I believe the topics to be taught are interesting.	2.14	Low	2.42	Low	2.34	Low	2.17	Low	2.38	Low	2.29 (Low)
Average	2.61	High	2.59	High	2.63	High	2.6	High	2.7	High	2.63 (High)
Peer Involvement											
My peers made me feel the sense of being in the right place.	2.79	High	2.58	High	2.72	High	2.74	High	3.0	High	2.77 (High)
My classmate helped me resolve difficult problems with modular activities.	2.50	High	2.67	High	2.31	Low	2.61	High	2.38	Low	2.49 (Low)
Among my classmates' responses to answer questions that I struggle a lot.	2.43	Low	2.33	Low	2.41	Low	2.48	Low	2.38	Low	2.41 (Low)
Among my friends helped me when I do not understand a concept taught in my module.	2.64	High	2.79	High	2.62	High	2.78	High	2.63	High	2.69 (High)
Among my friends support my learning needs.	3.29	Very High	3.33	Very High	3.17	High	3.26	Very High	3.63	Very High	3.34 (Very High)
Average	2.73	High	2.74	High	2.65	High	2.77	High	2.80	High	2.74 (High)
Family/Parent Involvement											
My parents encouraged me to study.	3.93	Very High	3.52	Very High	3.72	Very High	3.57	Very High	3.63	Very High	3.67 (Very High)
Among my family directed me on how to do the activities of the lesson.	2.00	Low	2.21	Low	2.14	Low	2.3	Low	2.13	Low	2.15 (Low)
My family provided my study-needs in self-learning.	2.43	Low	2.45	Low	2.24	Low	2.39	Low	2.38	Low	2.37 (Low)
Among my family responses every time I struggle dealing with problems the I encounter.	2.64	High	2.64	High	2.79	High	2.65	High	2.63	High	2.67 (High)
My family's economic status induced me to study.	4.00	Very High	4.00	Very High	4.00	Very High	4.00	Very High	4.00	Very High	4.00 (Very High)
Average	3.00	High	2.96	High	2.978	High	2.982	High	2.95	High	2.97 (High)
Teacher Involvement											
The teachers are supported to us students this pandemic time.	3.43	High	3.58	Very High	3.53	Very High	3.30	High	4.00	Very High	3.57 (Very High)
Our teachers made us understand the importance of studying.	3.64	Very High	3.61	Very High	3.41	High	3.52	Very High	3.75	Very High	3.59 (Very High)
The teachers care for us whenever we have needs.	3.50	Very High	3.36	High	3.31	High	3.39	High	4.00	Very High	3.51 (Very High)
Our teachers advised and encouraged us occasionally to boost our interest.	2.93	High	3.12	High	3.45	High	3.22	High	3.00	High	3.14 (High)
My teachers inspired me by their commitment.	3.14	High	3.06	High	3.55	Very High	3.22	High	3.00	High	3.19 (High)
Average	3.328	High	3.35	High	3.45	High	3.33	High	3.55	Very High	3.4 (Very High)
Learning Environment											
There is no need to travel that takes a lot of time.	3.64	Very High	3.7	Very High	3.69	Very High	3.57	Very High	3.25	High	3.57 (Very High)
The setting of learning can provide immediate help from the family.	2.14	Low	2.36	Low	2.41	High	2.39	Low	2.38	Low	2.34 (Low)
The place of learning is safe from the emerging disease called COVID-19.	3.93	Very High	3.88	Very High	3.93	Very High	3.83	Very High	4.00	Very High	3.91 (Very High)
Anything that I can use dealing with the modules is accessible at home.	2.14	Low	2.18	Low	2.28	Low	2.22	Low	2.25	Low	2.21 (Low)
Home-schooling will be cheaper unlike if you are in school.	2.07	Low	2.42	High	2.17	Low	2.21	Low	2.25	Low	2.22 (Low)
Average	2.78	High	2.91	High	2.90	High	2.84	High	2.83	High	2.85 (High)

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data gathered, the following conclusions were established:

1. Teachers' involvement in IP learners' education during the Covid-19 pandemic was high; the support, advice, encouragement, care, and commitment motivated the IP learners at the different IP schools.
2. Based on the study's findings, an intervention program elevating the level of personal interest, peer involvement, learning environment, and parent/family involvement will focus on motivating IP learners' education.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it may be recommended that:

1. School faculty organizations in the public IP schools must conduct home-visitation among IP learners to facilitate and uplift their interest in keeping their education.
2. School faculty organization will work "ICT integration seminar-workshop" for the IP learners at the IP schools to develop their will and level of performance.
3. School faculty organizations will "conduct parent-mentoring seminar workshops" to build their involvement in their children's education and improve learning settings amidst pandemics.
4. Finally, this study recommends creating a survey in remote communities to reinforce learners' education. It will be initiated by teachers and with the help of other stakeholders, ensuring learners' learning amidst struggles and challenges. It, in turn, augments or strengthens the morale of the IP learners resulting in productivity and high performance.

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